

Research Mapping around the Determinant Variables of Return on Assets (ROA) in Islamic Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around Return On Assets/ROA in Islamic Banking. The research was conducted from 2011 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "Return On Assets". Based on the search results, there were 114 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a Library Research study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Return On Assets/ROA is divided into 8 clusters and 123 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a Library Research study, there are 3 main themes related to Return On Assets/ROA in Islamic Banking.

Keywords: Return On Assets (ROA), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Library Research, Islamic Banking

Introduction

Return on Assets (ROA) is one of the ratios used to assess the condition of a company. Investors can determine the success of a company based on measuring the net profit generated by the company through the use of assets. Good ROA always indicates great value because ROA describes how well the company's assets are managed. Good asset management will have an impact on increasing company growth and the resulting profits will be greater. Islamic Banking is part of sharia-based financial institutions. The basic concept is to carry out operational activities based on sharia law principles. Sharia compliance is the basis for the obligation to implement sharia principles established by institutions that have authority in sharia supervision, such as the National Sharia Council (DSN). DSN is tasked with issuing fatwas regarding Islamic Banking. Profits in Islamic banking occur because there is a difference in value between the funds collected and the funds distributed.

In previous research, it was important for Islamic Banking to be able to control the effectiveness of its assets. ROA can be used to determine the size of the assets owned by Islamic banks as well as the ability of Islamic banks to generate profits based on the assets owned. ROA functions as the dependent variable while the other variables function as independent variables. In nonparametric regression analysis, it is not assumed that the relationship between the dependent and independent variables has a certain form. Instead, the form of this relationship will be estimated directly from existing data. Kernel and spline methods are two techniques that can be used to perform this estimation. Kernel methods use kernel functions to smooth data and estimate relationships between variables. Meanwhile, the spline method uses polynomial functions that are connected smoothly to estimate the relationship between variables.

ROA and other variables that influence Islamic Banking performance will be considered as an interacting system. In VAR analysis, related variables are connected through mathematical equations that describe the cause-and-effect relationship between these variables. In measuring ROA using the VAR method, it is important to take into account interactions between variables that can influence Islamic Banking performance. Some examples of variables that can be included in VAR analysis include company size, asset quality, liquidity, and so on.

Every year, scientific publications regarding ROA in Sharia Banks continue to increase. There are 114 studies on the Garuda Digital Reference (Garuda) website that discuss ROA in Islamic Banking until 2022. This shows that research on ROA in Islamic Banking is of great interest to researchers. The aim of this research is to determine the development map of research discussing ROA in Islamic banking in Indonesia over a period of twelve years (2011-2022) using the VOSviewer bibliometric method and Library Research.

Literature Review

Return on Assets (ROA) is a financial ratio used to measure the efficiency of using assets to generate profits. ROA is calculated by dividing a bank's net profit by its total assets. ROA is one of the main performance indicators used to evaluate the financial performance of a bank. In the context of Islamic banking, ROA is calculated by considering sharia principles which prohibit riba (interest) and promote risk sharing between the parties involved. Therefore, ROA in Islamic banking does not only include interest income, but also profits generated from investment or financing activities based on profit and loss sharing (profit sharing). In practice, Islamic banking usually has a lower ROA compared to conventional banks, because they do not offer interest-bearing products such as term deposits and interest-bearing loans. However, low ROA does not always indicate poor performance, because Islamic banking can choose to prioritize sustainable growth and social and environmental responsibility, above high profits.

$$\text{Return On Assets (ROA)} = \frac{\text{Laba Setelah Pajak} \times 100\%}{\text{Total Aset}}$$

Bibliometric mapping is a branch of science that studies the publication and distribution of scientific publications and analyzes the relationship between publications and authors, institutions, or research fields. Bibliometric studies utilize statistical methodologies and analytical techniques to assess and analyze the production and impact of scientific publications. The purpose of bibliometric studies is to provide insight into trends and patterns in scientific publications, help determine research priorities and funding, and help determine the productivity and impact of individuals or institutions in a field of research. Bibliometric studies are often used in the fields of social and natural sciences to understand evolution and trends in research and help make strategic decisions in funding and research.

VOSviewer is an application used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. This application is used to help researchers and analysts evaluate trends and patterns in scientific publications, and to help determine relationships between publications, authors, and institutions. VOSviewer uses visualization techniques such as network analysis and bibliometric maps to provide a visual representation of publications and relationships between

publications. It helps researchers assess the productivity and impact of an individual, institution, or research field. VOSviewer can also be used to map trends and developments in the research field and help make strategic decisions in funding and research.

Library Research is a process of systematic and critical evaluation of written sources (such as scientific journals, books, and other documents) to understand and evaluate the level of existing knowledge and research on the topic under study. The purpose of a Library Research study is to provide an overview of what is already known about the topic and to determine directions for further research. Library Research studies also help in identifying gaps in knowledge and determining what needs to be known next.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is Return On Assets (ROA) in Sharia Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Return On Assets (ROA) originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Return On Assets " for the entire year (20 11 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on Library Research studies.

Results and Discussion

1. Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Return on Assets (ROA) in Sharia Financial Institutions

Based on searches from 2011 to 2022, scientific publications containing discussions of Return on Assets (ROA) in Islamic banking in Indonesia illustrate that there are fluctuations in the number of publications carried out each year. However, these fluctuation conditions tend to increase compared to previous years. This is shown by the number of publications in 2021 which reached a total of 21 articles or around 18.10% over the last eleven years.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Return on Assets (ROA) by year

Year Publishing	Amount Article	Percentage	Year Publishing	Amount Article	Percentage
2011	1	0.87%	2018	11	9.64%

2014	5	4.38%	2019	17	14.91%
2015	6	5.26%	2020	13	11.40%
2016	10	8.77%	2021	21	18.42%
2017	14	12.28%	2022	16	14.03%
Total 114					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Based on table 1, there are 114 scientific articles discussing Return on Assets in Islamic Banking that have been published. This is published on the Digital Reference Garba (Garuda) website

Furthermore, there are 3 rankings if sorted based on the most institutions/affiliations that are actively publishing research articles related to ROA in Islamic Banking. The affiliate/institution that publishes scientific articles is the FEB Student Scientific Journal, with 5 publications in the last eleven years.

Table 2. Affiliation/institution of journal publishers about Return on Assets (ROA)

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
FEB Student Scientific Journal	5
Masharif al-Syariah Journal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking	3
An-Nisbah: Journal of Sharia Economics, JYRS: Online Journal for Students of the Faculty of Sharia and Islamic Economics Study Program, Actual Journal of Applied Business Financial Accounting (AKUNBISNIS), Students Journal of Accounting and Banking, el-Amwal, Jurnal Curvanomic.	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

The most productive researcher writing about Return On Assets (ROA) in Sharia Financial Institutions is Udik Jatmiko from Kadiri Islamic University, Kediri, with 2 journal articles. Meanwhile, other researchers only wrote 1 journal article.

2. Bibliometric Mapping Research regarding Return on Assets (ROA) in Sharia Financial Institutions

Based on search results on the Garba Referral Digital (Garuda) website, 114 research articles were found that discussed Return on Assets (ROA). Next, the data is downloaded from the research article in RIS (Research Information Systems) format. This data will be processed using VOSViewer software and analyzed. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Return on Assets (ROA)

Source: Data processed, software VOSViewer 1. 6. 18

The results of data processing obtained 8 clusters and 123 topics which are visualized in Figure 1 as follows:

- Cluster 1, red, consists of 19 topics, namely: Bank Mandiri Syariah, company size, country, data collection, economy, environment, funding, intervening, investment, investors. Islamic social reporting, leverage, easyrabah financing, musyarakah financing, path analysis, positive influence, quantitative method, SBI, SBIS.
- Cluster 2, green consists of 18 topics, namely: CAR influence analysis, inflation influence analysis, Islamic bank assets, autocorrelation, Bank Muamalat Indonesia, business, classical assumptions, empirical study, GDP, heteroscedasticity, inflation, influence analysis, murabahah margin, money supply, multiple linear regression, financial services authority, performing finance.
- Cluster 3, blue consists of 19 topics, namely: conventional bank, financial services author, ijarah, ijarah financing, income, insignificant effect, istishna, murabahah, murabahah financing, operating expense, panel data, predictive ability, public, purposive study, regression test, saving, stationary test.
- Cluster 4, yellow consists of 17 topics, namely: achievement, financial report analysis, bank size, BOPO variable, capital adequacy, dependent variable, determinant return, development, empirical evidence, fund, GCG, IB vaic, intellectual capital, operation, panel data regression, term, total assets.
- Cluster 5, purple consists of 16 topics, namely: ability, according, assessment, bank muamalat, earning asset quality, fourth quarter, KAP, liquidity, measurement, multiple linear regression, Persero, quantitative research, risk, secondary data type, significant level, theory.
- Cluster 6, light blue consists of 13 topics, namely: return analysis, autocorrelation, Indonesian people's banks, quantitative, financial reports,

multiple linear, multicolonierita, musyarakah, value, partial test, mudharabah financing, GIS, normality test.

- Cluster 7, orange consists of 10 topics, namely: autocorrelation test, cost, entire population, heteroscedasticity test, hypothesis test, interest test, mudharabah deposit, multicollinearity, profit sharing, quarterly financial starter, regression model.
- Cluster 8, brown consists of 11 topics, namely: BCA Syariah, BNI Syariah, BRI Syariah, descriptive test, FDR ratio, Mandiri Syariah, DPK growth, profitability, REO, ROA ratio.

3. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Determinant Variables of Return on Assets/ROA in Islamic Banking

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 46 variables determining Return On Assets/ROA, namely:

(1) Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR. The higher the FDR, the more financing provided by the bank compared to the deposits received. The influence of FDR on ROA in Islamic banking can vary depending on economic conditions, market structure and bank business strategy. However, in general, the higher the FDR, the higher the bank's risk because fewer sources of funds are available to invest in safer instruments. This can result in banks becoming more vulnerable to credit, liquidity and operational risks.

(2) Third Party Funds/DPK. The effect of TPF on ROA in Islamic Banking is usually positive, because the higher the DPK, the more funds available to invest and the smaller the bank's risk. However, banks must also take into account the costs incurred to obtain TPF, such as deposit interest paid to customers.

(3) Inflation. Inflation can influence ROA in Islamic banking in two ways, namely the influence on operational costs and the influence on asset quality. Increased inflation tends to increase bank operational costs because it increases production costs and expenses. Apart from that, inflation can also affect asset quality because it can cause a decrease in the real value of assets owned by the bank. Therefore, Islamic banking must consider inflation factors in its business strategy, including in setting interest rates and credit risk management. Thus, the influence of inflation on ROA in Islamic banking tends to be negative.

(4) BI Rate. The influence of the BI Rate on ROA in Islamic Banking can vary depending on economic conditions and the bank's business strategy. In general, an increase in the BI Rate can reduce loan demand and increase the interest burden for customers, thereby reducing ROA in Islamic Banking. However, if the bank can adjust loan and deposit interest rates to the BI Rate appropriately, the bank can benefit from a larger interest difference and increase ROA.

(5) Domestic Product Growth. Domestic product (GDP) growth can influence ROA in Islamic Banking because economic growth can increase demand for credit and strengthen customers' ability to repay loans. Therefore, if GDP growth increases, then demand for credit may increase and banks may profit from higher interest rates. Apart from that, stable and high GDP growth can also strengthen the quality of bank assets and increase ROA in Islamic Banking.

(6) Non Performing Financing/NPF. The influence of NPF on ROA in Islamic banking is very significant, because problematic financing can worsen the quality of bank assets and reduce ROA. Therefore, banks must manage credit risk well, including tightening credit granting criteria and carrying out strict monitoring of the financing provided. Banks must also have loss reserves to overcome the risk of problematic financing that may occur.

(7) Quality of Productive Assets/KAP/Earnings Asset Quality. The influence of KAP on ROA in Islamic Banking is very important, because the lower the KAP ratio, the better the quality of the bank's assets and the higher the ROA that can be achieved. Therefore, banks must ensure that providing credit to customers is followed by good credit evaluation and strict supervision to reduce credit risk.

(8) Non Performing Loans/NPL. The influence of NPL on ROA in Islamic banking is very significant, because the higher the NPL, the worse the quality of the bank's assets and the lower the ROA that can be achieved.

(9) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. The influence of CAR on ROA in Islamic banking can vary depending on the bank's business strategy and applicable regulatory policies. In general, a higher CAR can increase investor and customer confidence, thereby increasing demand for credit and strengthening the bank's ability to provide better credit. However, a CAR that is too high can also hamper the bank's business growth and reduce the ROA that can be achieved.

(10) Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO. The lower the BOPO ratio, the more efficient the bank is in managing operational costs and the greater the potential profits that can be obtained. In the context of Islamic Banking, a low BOPO can also reflect the level of efficiency in implementing sharia principles in bank operations.

(11) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. The higher the LDR, the greater the credit risk taken by the bank. However, the lower the LDR, the smaller the bank's ability to provide credit to its customers. Therefore, Islamic banks need to find a balance between credit risk and business growth by maintaining a healthy LDR. If the bank succeeds in maintaining a healthy LDR, the potential ROA of Islamic banks will also increase.

(12) Company size. Company size can also influence ROA in Islamic banking. The larger the company size, the greater the opportunity to gain greater profits through economies of scale and risk diversification. However, the larger the company, the more complicated the organizational structure and the more difficult it is to manage risk.

(13) Zakat. Zakat is one component of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) carried out by sharia banks. When a sharia bank pays zakat, this can affect its ROA because zakat expenditure reduces the profits earned by the bank. However, paying zakat can also provide long-term benefits for Islamic banks, such as increasing the positive image and public trust in the bank.

(14) Ijarah Income. Ijarah income is a sharia bank's income from renting or leasing the productive assets it owns. If a sharia bank has a large enough and well-diversified asset portfolio, then Ijarah income can make a significant contribution to ROA. However, if the Islamic bank does not have an adequate asset portfolio, then Ijarah income will not have a significant impact on ROA.

(15) Mudharabah and Musyarakah profit sharing income. Mudharabah and Musyarakah profit sharing income is sharia bank income that comes from collaboration with third parties in the form of financing or investment. If a sharia bank succeeds in establishing a solid partnership with a third party and is successful in choosing the right project, then Mudharabah and Musyarakah profit sharing income can make a significant contribution to the ROA of the sharia bank.

(16) Musyarakah, Murabahah, Istishna, Qardh, Ijarah and Mudharabah financing. The effect of Musyarakah financing on ROA in Islamic Banking can increase ROA, because the bank will share profits with customers and these profits can increase bank assets. Murabahah is a type of financing carried out

by purchasing goods by a sharia bank and then reselling them to customers at a higher price. Customers pay higher prices periodically or at one time. The effect of Murabahah financing on ROA in Islamic Banking can increase ROA, because the bank will gain profits from the resale of the goods. Istishna is a type of financing carried out by sharia banks ordering certain goods from producers and selling them to customers at a higher price. Customers pay higher prices periodically or at one time. The effect of Istishna financing on ROA in Islamic Banking can also increase ROA, because the bank will gain profits from the resale of the goods. Qardh financing is a type of financing provided without providing profits to the bank. In this case, the bank only provides loans without any compensation. The impact on ROA is not that big, because the bank does not gain direct profits from this financing. However, Qardh financing can help banks retain customers and improve the bank's image. Ijarah financing is a type of financing carried out using the leasing principle. Banks buy certain goods or assets and rent them to customers in exchange for rent. The impact on ROA is relatively stable, because the bank makes a profit from the rent given to customers. However, ROA can be influenced by the quality of the leased assets and the bank's risk management policies. Mudharabah financing is a type of financing carried out with the principle of profit sharing between the bank and the customer. Banks act as investors and customers as entrepreneurs. Profits from the business carried out will be shared between the bank and the customer in accordance with the agreed agreement. The impact on ROA is greatly influenced by the established profit sharing agreement. If the deal is profitable for the bank, then ROA will increase. However, if the deal is profitable for the customer, then ROA will decrease.

(17) Murabahah Margin. Murabahah margin in Islamic Banking has a big influence on ROA, because it is one of the main sources of income from Islamic Banking. The higher the Murabahah Margin, the greater the profits obtained by Islamic Banking, so that the ROA will increase.

(18) Net Operating Margin/NOM. NOM also influences ROA in Islamic Banking, because it is an indicator of bank performance efficiency in managing income and operational costs. The higher the NOM, the more efficient the bank's performance in managing income and operational costs, so that its ROA will increase.

(19) Human Resources. HR is an important factor in influencing ROA in Islamic Banking. Quality and competent human resources can improve bank performance in providing services to customers, as well as being able to run bank operations well. This will have an impact on customer trust in the bank, thereby increasing the number of customers and transactions carried out. On the other hand, if human resources are not of good quality, the bank's performance will decrease, so that its ROA will also decrease.

(20) Risk management. Effective risk management can increase ROA in Islamic banking because it can reduce the risk of loss and increase customer trust. This can be achieved by implementing good risk management practices in managing credit risk, operational risk, market risk, liquidity risk and reputation risk.

(21) Gross Domestic Product/GDP. GDP can influence ROA in Islamic banking because good economic growth can increase demand and business growth in the banking sector. The higher the GDP growth, the more opportunities available for Islamic banking to earn greater profits, and thereby increase ROA.

(22) Islamic Social Reporting/ISR. ISR can influence ROA in Islamic banking because it can strengthen the image of sustainable and socially responsible Islamic banking. This can be achieved by providing transparent reports on the

social, environmental and economic activities of Islamic banking. This can increase customer trust and encourage long-term business growth, which in turn can increase ROA.

(23) Intellectual Capital. Intellectual Capital can influence ROA in Islamic banking because IC is an intangible asset that can improve company performance. IC components include human capital, structural capital, and relational capital. Human capital can improve company performance through the quality of human resources and productivity. Structural capital can increase a company's efficiency and effectiveness through the systems, procedures and technology used. Relational capital can improve company performance through good relationships with customers, investors and other related parties.

(24) Fee Based Income/FBI. Fee Based Income can influence ROA in Islamic Banking because it can increase income that does not depend on interest margins. Fee Based Income can be obtained from various sources such as financial services, investment management services, and consulting services. With this alternative source of income, Islamic banking can increase income diversification and reduce dependence on interest. This can help Islamic banking maintain a stable ROA and increase profits in the future.

(25) Mergers. Mergers can affect ROA in Islamic Banking by increasing the scale and scope of the company's business. Through mergers, Islamic banking can expand the market and increase market share. With a larger business scale, Islamic banking can achieve higher efficiency and increase revenue through combining resources and infrastructure. However, mergers can also introduce new risks such as integration risk and concentration risk.

(26) Bank Indonesia Sharia/SBIS Certificate. SBIS issuance has a positive influence on Return On Assets (ROA) in Islamic Banking. This is because the issuance of SBIS can increase Islamic Banking capital which can be used to improve asset quality and reduce credit risk. In addition, investor confidence in Islamic Banking can increase if the bank issues SBIS, thereby increasing banking liquidity and overall financial performance.

(27) Currency exchange rates. The influence of currency exchange rates on ROA in Islamic banking can be positive or negative, depending on the direction of changes in exchange rates. If the foreign currency exchange rate appreciates, the value of assets denominated in foreign currency will increase, thereby increasing ROA. Conversely, if the foreign currency exchange rate experiences depreciation, the value of assets denominated in foreign currency will decrease, thereby reducing ROA.

(28) Operational risk. The influence of operational risk on ROA in Islamic Banking is negative. If operational risk increases, Islamic Banking operational costs will increase, thereby reducing ROA. Apart from that, operational risk can also reduce customer trust in Islamic Banking, thereby reducing the amount of funds held by Islamic Banking and overall financial performance.

(29) Return On Capital Employed/ROCE. ROCE is a financial ratio used to measure a company's ability to generate profits from invested capital. The higher the ROCE, the better the company's performance. ROCE can affect ROA because the higher the ROCE, the higher the rate of return on capital generated by Islamic banks. This can increase ROA because Islamic banks can generate greater profits from the assets they own.

(30) Economic Value Added/EVA. EVA is a financial performance measurement method that measures the profit generated by a company after deducting the cost of capital. EVA can affect ROA in Islamic banks because the higher the EVA value, the greater the profit generated by Islamic banks after deducting the cost

of capital. This can increase ROA because Islamic banks can generate greater profits from the assets they own.

(31) Net Interest Margin/NIM. NIM is the difference between the interest received by the bank and the interest paid by the bank on the funds received. NIM can influence ROA at Islamic banks because the higher the NIM, the greater the profits generated by Islamic banks from their credit operations. This can increase ROA because Islamic banks can generate greater profits from the assets they own.

(32) Minimum Capital Requirement/KPMM. KPMM has a significant influence on Return On Assets (ROA) in Islamic Banking. The higher the ratio of KPMM to total assets, the lower the ROA. This is because the greater the capital requirement, the higher the capital costs that must be incurred by the bank.

(33) Money supply. The amount of money in circulation has an influence on ROA in Islamic Banking because Islamic Banking is a financial institution that plays a role in creating and managing money. The higher the money supply, the greater the public's need to carry out financial transactions and the greater the potential income for Islamic Banking. However, it is important to remember that the money supply is also influenced by macroeconomic factors such as inflation and economic growth.

(34) Quick Ratio. Quick Ratio has a significant influence on ROA in Islamic Banking because the bank's ability to fulfill current obligations is very important to maintain bank credibility and customer trust. The higher the Quick Ratio, the better the bank's ability to fulfill current obligations, the higher the ROA will be. However, a Quick Ratio that is too high can also indicate that the bank has too high liquidity and is inefficient in managing its assets.

(35) Current Ratio. The higher the current ratio, the more liquid the bank, meaning the bank is better able to meet its short-term obligations. In this case, the current ratio can influence ROA positively, because the more liquid the bank, the less risk the bank will experience liquidity difficulties. This can increase investor confidence and can influence the bank's overall performance.

(36) Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. The higher the DER, the greater the bank's risk of changes in interest rates and bankruptcy risk. In this case, DER can affect ROA negatively, because the higher the DER, the greater the interest burden the bank must bear and the greater the risk the bank faces. This can cause a decrease in bank profits and reduce overall ROA.

(37) Total assets. The greater the total assets, the greater the bank's ability to provide loans and increase income. In this case, total assets can influence ROA positively, because the greater the total assets, the greater the bank's ability to generate income and increase profits. However, if a bank cannot manage its assets effectively, large total assets can lead to higher operational risk and credit risk, which can reduce ROA.

(38) Operational Efficiency Ratio/OER. The lower the OER, the more efficient the bank is in managing its operational costs. In this case, OER can influence ROA positively, because the more efficient the bank, the less costs it has to incur to generate the same income. This can increase bank profits and increase overall ROA.

(39) Net Profit Margin/NPM. The higher the NPM, the greater the bank's net profit compared to its income. In this case, NPM can influence ROA positively, because the greater the bank's net profit, the greater the bank's ability to generate higher ROA. However, a high NPM can also indicate that the bank may not be lending aggressively enough or may have lower credit risk.

(40) Gross Profit Margin/GPM. The higher the GPM, the greater the bank's gross profit compared to its income. In this case, GPM can influence ROA positively, because the greater the bank's gross profit, the greater the bank's ability to obtain higher income and produce a higher ROA. However, like NPM, a high GPM can also indicate that a bank may not be lending aggressively enough or may have lower credit risk.

(41) Debt to Asset Ratio/DAR. The higher the DAR, the greater the risk of company bankruptcy because the more debt must be paid. In this case, DAR can negatively affect ROA, because the more debt that must be paid, the less profit is available to generate ROA. However, in some cases, a high DAR can indicate that the bank is expanding its business and making investments that could increase ROA in the future.

(42) Spin-Off. In this case, a Spin-Off can affect ROA positively or negatively depending on the context. If the separated business unit has poor financial performance, a Spin-Off can improve overall ROA by separating risks and increasing focus on more profitable business units. However, if the separated business unit has good financial performance, the Spin-Off can reduce the ROA by reducing the bank's assets and income.

(43) Net Rewards. In this case, Net Benefits can affect ROA negatively, because increasing the cost of pension benefits can reduce the company's net profit and reduce ROA. However, low Net Rewards can increase ROA by increasing the company's net profit.

(44) Promotional costs. Promotional costs can affect ROA positively or negatively depending on the effectiveness of the promotional campaign. If a promotional campaign is successful in increasing the number of customers and transactions, Promotional Fees can provide a higher return on investment and increase ROA. However, if the promotional campaign is unsuccessful in attracting new customers or increasing the number of transactions, Promotional Costs can reduce bank profits and reduce ROA.

(45) MSME Financing. MSME financing can positively influence ROA by increasing bank income from interest and profits from additional products and services. Apart from that, MSME financing can also help banks expand their customer base and increase future income potential. However, MSME financing also has high credit risk, so if payment failure or bad credit occurs, this can negatively affect ROA.

(46) Murabaha Receivables. Murabahah receivables can positively influence ROA by increasing bank income from interest and profits from murabahah products. However, if late payments or defaults occur, this can negatively affect ROA by increasing credit risk and higher collection costs.

4. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Return on Assets/ROA on Islamic Banking

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 16 influences caused by Return On Assets/ROA, namely:

(1) Sharing the profits from Mudharabah deposits. The influence of ROA on the profit sharing of mudharabah deposits will depend on the perspective of the bank as a fund manager and the customer as a depositor. In general, the higher the ROA generated by a bank, the greater the possibility of profit sharing that will be provided to customers. This is because the bank has sufficient profits to share part of the profits it earns.

(2) Musyarakah, Mudharabah and Murabahah financing. For the Musyarakah type of financing, a high ROA can increase partners' trust in the transaction

because it shows the company's ability to generate profits together. Meanwhile, for the Mudharabah type of financing, a high ROA can increase investor confidence because it shows the company's ability to gain profits from the investments made. Meanwhile, in the Murabahah type of financing, the influence of ROA tends to be smaller because this type of financing is more related to goods buying and selling transactions, so ROA is not a very significant factor in these transactions.

(3) Islamic Social Reporting/ISR. ROA can have a positive influence on ISR in Islamic Banking because profits generated by banks can be used to fund social programs and activities that comply with sharia principles. Apart from that, Islamic banks are also expected to fulfill their social obligations in accordance with sharia principles.

(4) Liquidity risk. ROA has a negative influence on liquidity risk in Islamic Banking. The higher the ROA, the more resources available to the bank, which allows the bank to have more liquidity and reduces liquidity risk. However, it should be noted that excessive liquidity can also reduce ROA, so banks need to find the right balance between ROA and liquidity risk.

(5) Company value. ROA has a positive influence on company value in Islamic Banking. The higher the ROA, the more profits generated by the bank, and the higher the company value. Company value can also increase if the bank is able to optimize the use of resources and reduce operational costs.

(6) Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR. ROA can affect FDR because FDR is a ratio that measures how much the bank lends the money it gets from customer deposits. The higher the ROA, the greater the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns, so the bank will have greater funds to lend and increase FDR. However, if the ROA is too high, the bank may prefer to invest its money in more liquid and safe assets, so that the FDR can decrease.

(7) Income Smoothing. ROA can influence income smoothing because the higher the ROA, the easier it is for the bank to carry out income smoothing because the profits generated are quite large. However, if the ROA is too high, the bank may face moral risks in carrying out income smoothing which could be detrimental to stakeholders.

(8) Murabahah Margin. ROA can affect the murabahah margin because the higher the ROA, the greater the bank's ability to set a higher murabahah margin because the bank has greater bargaining power. However, if the ROA is too high, the bank may face reputational and regulatory risks that could suppress the resulting murabahah margin.

(9) Debt Financing. Increasing ROA in Islamic Banking tends to increase the bank's ability to obtain loan funds (debt financing) from outside parties, because the higher the ROA, the more efficient the use of assets in generating profits. Thus, Islamic banking will be considered more creditable by outside parties and will have the ability to obtain loans at lower interest rates.

(10) Total assets. Increasing ROA in Islamic Banking also tends to increase total banking assets. The increase in ROA shows that Islamic Banking is able to generate greater profits with the assets it owns, so that it can attract investors to invest their capital in Islamic Banking. By increasing the capital owned, Islamic Banking can develop its business by increasing the number of assets.

(11) Working capital financing. Increasing ROA in Islamic Banking also tends to increase banks' ability to provide working capital financing to customers. The higher the ROA, the greater the profits obtained by Islamic Banking, so that it can offer lower interest rates on working capital financing products. This will

attract customers' interest in choosing Islamic Banking as their business partner.

(12) Share price. ROA can affect the share price of a company, including Islamic Banking. If the company's ROA increases, then this shows good company performance and can increase investor confidence in the company. That way, the company's share price can increase due to increased investor confidence in the company's performance.

(13) Mudharabah Savings. ROA can also influence the amount of mudharabah savings received by Islamic Banking. If the company's ROA increases, then this shows the company's good performance in managing assets. That way, customers can entrust their funds to the company and increase the amount of mudharabah savings received by the company.

(14) Stock returns. ROA can also influence a company's stock returns. If the company's ROA increases, then this shows good company performance and can increase investor confidence in the company. That way, investors can buy shares in the company and expect higher returns because of the company's good performance.

(15) Market Share. ROA is an important financial performance indicator for Islamic banking, which can influence Market Share. The higher the ROA generated by Islamic Banking, the greater the possibility of gaining customer trust and increasing the Islamic Banking market share. This is because a high ROA shows the ability of Islamic banking to generate good profits from the assets it owns. In the long term, this can increase customer trust and have a positive impact on the growth of the Islamic Banking business.

(16) Share Price. ROA can also influence the share price of Islamic banking. A high ROA can indicate that Islamic banking is able to generate good profits and manage assets well. This can provide a positive signal to investors and encourage them to buy Islamic banking shares, thereby increasing the demand and price of Islamic banking shares. On the other hand, low ROA can raise investors' concerns about the financial performance of Islamic banking, which can cause a decline in Islamic banking share prices.

5. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Return On Assets/ROA Performance Measurement Methods in Islamic Banking

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 4 methods for measuring Return On Assets/ROA performance, namely:

First, Kernel and Spline Nonparametric Regression. Kernel and spline nonparametric regression methods can be used to measure the relationship between ROA and other variables that can influence Islamic banking performance, such as company size, liquidity, asset quality, and so on. In this case, ROA functions as the dependent variable while the other variables function as independent variables. In nonparametric regression analysis, it is not assumed that the relationship between the dependent and independent variables has a certain form. Instead, the form of this relationship will be estimated directly from existing data. Kernel and spline methods are two techniques that can be used to perform this estimation. Kernel methods use kernel functions to smooth data and estimate relationships between variables. Meanwhile, the spline method uses polynomial functions that are connected smoothly to estimate the relationship between variables.

Second, Vector Autoregression/VAR on Interrelationship. The Vector Autoregression (VAR) method is used to measure the relationship between several variables simultaneously. In this case, ROA and other variables that

influence Islamic Banking performance will be considered as an interacting system. In VAR analysis, related variables are connected through mathematical equations that describe the cause-and-effect relationship between these variables. In measuring ROA using the VAR method, it is important to take into account interactions between variables that can influence Islamic Banking performance. Some examples of variables that can be included in VAR analysis include company size, asset quality, liquidity, and so on.

Third, Intellectual Capital with iB-VAIC. This method consists of three main components, namely human capital, structural capital and customer capital. The following are the steps for measuring ROA using iB-VAIC in Islamic Banking:

- (1) Calculate the iB-VAIC value: In measuring iB-VAIC, there are three dimensions, namely Human Capital, Structural Capital, and Customer Capital. The iB-VAIC value is calculated by adding up the values of the three dimensions.
- (2) Calculate ROA: ROA can be calculated by dividing net profit by total assets. ROA can provide an idea of how effective a company is in generating profits from the assets it owns.
- (3) Analyze the relationship between iB-VAIC and ROA: After the iB-VAIC and ROA values are calculated, analyze the relationship between the two. This can be done using correlation or regression methods.

Fourth, the Modal/ECM Error Correction method. The ECM method is a time series data analysis method used to analyze long-term relationships between two or more variables. This method can be used to measure the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable at the same time. The following are the steps for measuring ROA using the ECM method in Islamic banking:

- (1) Variable identification: Identify the variables that will be used in the analysis, namely the independent variable and the dependent variable. In this case, the independent variables can be economic variables such as interest rates, inflation and stock market indexes, while the dependent variable is ROA.
- (2) ECM model estimation: After the variables have been identified, then estimate the ECM model. ECM model estimation can be done using statistical data processing software such as SPSS or Eviews.
- (3) Analysis of estimation results: After the ECM model has been estimated, analysis of the estimation results can be carried out to determine the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. This can be done by looking at the regression coefficient value and the significance level of each variable.
- (4) Interpretation of analysis results: The results of the analysis can be interpreted to draw conclusions regarding the influence of independent variables on ROA in Islamic banking. If the results of the analysis show that the independent variable has a significant positive influence on ROA, then this shows that Islamic banking can increase ROA by optimizing the use of the independent variable.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- Number of research publications around Return On Assets/ROA in Islamic Banking during the period 2011 to 2022, shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 114 research articles, which come from national journals indexed by Sinta.

- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the FEB Student Scientific Journal, with 5 publications in the last eleven years.
- The most productive researcher is Udik Jatmiko from Kadiri Islamic University, Kediri, with 2 journal articles.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Return On Assets/ROA in Islamic Banking are divided into 8 clusters and 123 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 19 topics, cluster 2 consists of 18 topics, cluster 3 consists of 19 topics, cluster 4 consists of 17 topics, cluster 5 consists of 16 topics, cluster 6 consists of 13 topics, cluster 7 consists of 10 topics, and cluster 8 consists of 11 topics.
- Based on the Library Research, there are 3 main research themes, namely: (1) Determinant variables; (2) The influence caused; and (3) Measurement method.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex way.

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